

ИСТОРИЯ ВОЕННО-УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В 1917-1941-Е ГОДЫ

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THE HISTORY OF MILITARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF UZBEKISTAN IN 1917-1941S

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Аннотация. Автор в данной статье проанализировал процесс становления военных училищ в течение 1917-1940 годов и деятельность этих военных училищ. В статье также были раскрыты выпускники военных училищ и курсов, социальный состав курсантов и роль этих военных училищ в развитии военного дела и военной истории Узбекистана. В статье также рассматривается история Среднеазиатского Национального военного училища, некогда являвшегося одним из единственных и основных военно-учебных заведений для республик Средней Азии, на основе периодических изданий газет и документов Российского государственного военного архива. В данной статье речь идет о Миркомиле Миршарапове (1900-1938), который учился в среднеазиатских военных училищах, а затем служил в узбекской горно-кавалерийской дивизии. Есть также сведения о знаменитых узбекских военных, таких как Юнус Нариманов (1898-1938).

Abstract. The author in this article has analyzed the process of formation of military schools during 1917-1940 years and activity of these military schools. In the article it was also revealed graduated cadets of military schools and courses, social composition of cadets and the role of these military schools in the progress of military work and military history in Uzbekistan. The article also examines the history of the Central Asian National Military School, which was once one of the only and basic military educational institutions for the Republics of Central Asia, based on periodicals newspapers and documents from the Russian State Military Archives. In this article we are talking about the Mirkomil Mirsharapov (1900-1938), who studied in the Central Asian military schools, and then served in the Uzbek mountain-cavalry division. There is also information about famous Uzbek military personnel, such as Yunus Narimanov (1898-1938).

Ключевые слова: военное училище, вооруженное сопротивление, командующий, Туркестанский фронт, курсант, Красная Армия, топография, солдат, эскадрилья, военный округ.

Keywords: military school, armed resistance, commander, Turkestan front, cadet, Red army, topography, soldier, squadron, Military district.

No matter which step of statehood history we look at, military fields and military specialists were specially paid attention by the states. Because internal policy of the state, security of state borders, peaceful life of the people mostly depended on the military fields too.

Military art began to develop in the first years of the statehood and reached the highest point of its progress during the reign of Amir Temur. After the Central Asian khanates had been conquered by the Tsar Russia, the tyrant policy of the Empire didn't go around the military field either like other different branches of the society. The administration of this government, who thought for the future, didn't want the local people to get arms into their hands and have military education, furthermore, they weren't involved in the military service at all, and even, the volunteers from the local people who wanted to be soldiers were not allowed either. One of the most insulting states was that wearing a knife, which was the custom for men in Turkistan, was also banned. This policy of the Tsar Russia carried out in the military field in Turkistan brought the local people to the lack of military education, a loss of interest to the military service, and even to avoid from being allotted to the national red army during the soviet government.

The armed resistance began against the Soviet system in Central Asia made the representatives of the Soviet government in Turkistan seriously think about the military field and involve the local people in the military service too.

The Soviet government began to fill the staff of the red army in Turkistan with the skilled, experienced military personnel who knew the language, national value and the local conditions of the native people, and establish military training courses and schools in order to train qualified, skilled military specialists. The main purpose of it was to use the native people, who knew well the geographical position of Turkistan, the language of the local people, their traditions and customs, religious values, local conditions, during the process of settling the armed resistance against soviet regime in Central Asia, and get rid of the relative nations living in the same country.

In the Republic of Turkistan in 1918, July 12 in Tashkent city the first Turkistan soviet commanders' course was opened in order to train military specialists from local people for the national units of worker farmer red army. The name of the course was changed to Turkistan military instructors' schools in 1919. In 1922 it was called Turkistan united commandership training school, in 1943 it was called Tashkent footsoldiers' school and in 1958 it was called general forces commandership school (from 1993, March 26 it was called Tashkent general forces commandership high school – R.E) [1, 194.].

Soviet government tried to establish several military commandership courses in Turkistan before the national-regional boundary. The main purpose of it was to make a national red army from local people and fill it with the national commanders knowing the local condition well. In this case it should be mentioned the information: “the relationships between the local people and the European red soldiers who didn't know well the life and condition of the local people were not established well yet”[2, 3.].

One of the important events carried out by the soviet government in teaching the military training to the local people in Turkistan was that the opening (establishment) of Turkistan national commandership course(school). This commandership course was opened in 1924 on June 15, in its opening ceremony the chief of Turkistan military revolutionary council, the deputy of the chairman of Turkistan Central Union Committee S.Khujanov participated. In the ceremony S.Khujanov talked about the military commandership course as “in this course there will be the representatives of every local nations”[3, 4.]. Rizo Yokubov was appointed as the first director of the commandership course.

Such kind of commandership schools were established in Bukhara, Khiva and Fergana cities too besides Tashkent. But later they were finished, and some of them were joined to another military. For example, After Bukhara People's Soviet Republic had been finished, Bukhara military school was transferred to Fergana. Later, the military school in Fergana was finished too and its teachers were brought to Tashkent [4, 35.].

About the first military commanders from the native people who studied at the military schools and the importance of this military school in Turkistan the "Kizil Bayraq" (Red Flag) [5] newspaper informed as "Up to that time there hadn't been red commanders to control the Muslim red soldiers, they were from other nations. It was difficult for our red soldiers to learn something from them. Considering these difficulties, in 1920 Turkistan republic opened Muslim red commanders course only for the youth of Turkistan. Although this course was a bit smaller than the courses in Tatar and Boshkird republics, it played an important role in the East." [6, 2.]. It can be concluded from the information given above that the national military commanders training schools in Turkistan were given great expectations.

The United national military school (1922-1927) – was founded under the name "Turkistan united commanders staff school" named by V.I.Lenin in Tashkent city on the basis of the order 1627/656 of Turkistan front on November 20, 1922. This school was established by uniting the military schools such as "Tashkent footsoldiers commandership school №23", "3-artillery course", "15-Oлмаота cavalry course" [7, 7.].

On the basis of the order of Revolutionary Military Council on November 18, 1922 it was renamed as "Tashkent united commanders school" named by V.I.Lenin in 1924, December 11 [8, 8.]. Tashkent united commanders school was named with different names in different years. From 1923, May 9 it was called "4- Tashkent united commanders school" named after V.I.Lenin [9, 26.], according to the order № 1265 of Revolutionary Military Council in 1924 it was called "United Tashkent military school" named after V.I.Lenin [10, 15.]. From 1924, December 19 it was renamed as "United military school" named after V.I.Lenin [11, 16.].

In order to teach the local people military education and train military specialists belonging to the native nation who know the life and the language of the local people well in 1924 November another 150 people "National Commandership course" was opened [12, 4.]. The listeners of this course were mainly Uzbek and then Kirgыз and Kazakhs. In order to widely involve the local people in the military education the Soviet government even promised to help financially the families of the youth who were sent to the military course. And this task was compulsorily given to the responsibility of all the organizations and parties.

The young people from many cities of Turkistan were sent to this military course. In the first step 18 people from Margilan uezd and 78 people from Kokand uezd were sent. According to the number of the cadets who came to study Fergana and Samarkand uezds stood in the second place. According to the information given in the newspaper "Turkistan" [13], in 1924 there were 141 cadets in the course, their social composition was comprised of the followings: The Uzbek – 107 people, the Kazakh – 16 people, the Karakalpak – 5 people, the Tajik -10 people, the native Tatar – 2 people, the Iranian – 1 person. The cadets in the military course studied in 3 military fields. In the first field – machinegunners faculty there were 30 Uzbek, 3 Kazakh, 1 Karakalpakian, 1 Tajik cadets, in the second field – communication faculty there were 28 Uzbek, 1 Tajik, 1 Kazakh cadets, in the third field – grenade launchers (mine and grenade) faculty there were 27 Uzbek, 10 Kazakh, 7 Tajik, 4 Karakalpakian, 2 native Tatarian, 1 Iranian cadets. Most of the cadets were about 20-23 year-old young people [14, 3.].

In the military course 55 commanders, political leaders, and teachers educated the cadets, 4 of them were Russian knowing the local language very well and the others were local teachers. According to the information in the national presses of that time in which the history of the military course was described, the cadets were very well supplied. There were enough educational buildings for the cadets to study, each course studied in a separate building. The cadets were provided with summer and winter clothes. The foods given to the cadets were also from the condition of the lifestyle of the local nations.

During the national regional boundary the armed resistance continuing in Turkistan against the Soviet regime also demanded the establishment of military school in Central Asia. About the reason of establishing the military schools the following information was given in the “Turkistan” newspaper in the article by A. Bobojonov “in the struggle with Basmachis (hist. name used for bands of Central Asian counter-revolutionaries in the 1920s) (armed resistance – R.E) the red soldiers from Russia and the results of their work openly showed the necessity of establishing national red army and made them establish it quickly. Because, the soldiers of the red army who were unfamiliar with the position, geographical situation of Turkistan and mentality of the people were again in need for the native local people to instruct and direct. Not knowing about the highlands, mountains, rivers mountain tracks and deserts the red soldiers tried for nonsense and got difficulties.

Secondly, the more the nation disliked the wild and cruel soldiers of Nikolay (the last emperor of Russia Nikolay II), the more they couldn't get used to the European soldiers of Soviets” [15, 2.].

The policy of national-regional boundary carried out by the soviet government in Central Asia caused serious changes to the United national military school's activity and its component structures. The staff of the military school was strictly adapted by Turkistan front because of the need for the middle class commanders formed on the basis of a 5-year plan for Central Asian republics and their autonomous provinces. According to the staff of the military school in 1925, in the rifle company of the school 174 cadets (82 Uzbek, 47 Kyrgyz, 1 Black Kyrgyz, 6 Tajik and 38 other nations), in mounted cavalry 98 cadets (26 Uzbek, 40 Turkmen, 14 Kyrgyz, 7 Black Kyrgyz, 8 Tajik and 3 other nations) got military education. In 1926 30 infantry and 18 mounted first red commanders (platoon commanders) graduated from the national school. According to the report of Turkistan front, from 1925-1926s 2 mounted cavalries were intended to be formed, a request was sent about it to the union of revolutionary military committee. From 1927 the staff of middle class commanders of the national military units of Central Asian republics and autonomous provinces was fully provided because of the graduates of this national school.

But the United military school didn't last long and was finished in 1927 on the 1 st of December. All its component units were given to the disposal of the new established “United Central Asian military school” [16, 43.]. The Soviet government adroitly used the military school in the struggle against the armed resistance begun against the soviet regime in Central Asia. The school participated in the military operations of the soviet government in order to finish the armed resistance in Oblik, Burchmulla and Chotkol valleys in 1923. During the short-term work of the military school it was run by Rizo Yokubov and Biyazi, Lutsenko, Zaks, Gorbunov, Khoroshilov were the military commissars.

In 1927 on December 3 military schools – the United Central Asian military school, Military political school and Tashkent united commanders school №4 named after V.I.Lenin were joined and became a single United Central Asian national military school.

United Central Asian national military school (1927-1940s) – the United Central Asian military school was established on the basis of the order 341 of the SSSR Revolutionary Military Committee in 1927 on August 21 under the name “the United Central Asian military school” named after V.I.Lenin. this school was established by joining “United military school” named after V.I.Lenin and “United Central Asian national military school” named after V.I.Lenin [17, 53.].

In the same year the school was established (in 1927) a 1-year term military-political course was organized. The first graduates finished this course in 1928, on August 1. The military-political course of the school prepared more than 200 cadets from 1928 till 1936. Besides the military-political course, a retraining course for commandership staff (1929-1931) and a training department (1927-1930) were established under school [18].

The military school participated in the military movements against Junaidkhan in 1927. In 1929-1930 s it actively participated in the military movements to finish the groups of armed resistance in Angren district of Tashkent, Suzok, Turkistan and Bustonlik districts of Sirdarya region. In 1931 it participated in the battles against the groups of armed resistance in Korabugiz and Korakum regions and finished them. The school was awarded with “Medal of Labour Red Flag of Turkmanistan SSR” of Turkmanistan SSR in 1931, on November 5 for the militaristic service in the military movements in Korakum [19, 316.].

The national military schools in Turkistan functioned not only to give local nation representatives a military education and raise local military specialists among them, but also to provide Russian high military schools with military specialists from the local people. Most of the Uzbek young people were educated in the military schools in Moscow, Kazan and Baku cities. In 1924-1926s 12 Uzbek youths were educated at the military school of Azarbeijan and 5 of them were educated at the Caspian military-training school as listeners [20, 34.].

At the Central Asian nations’ United military commandership school together with the cadets of different nations M.Mirsharapov (1900-1938), Yu.Narimonov (1898-1938), Y. Dadaboev (1901-1938), H.Isomiddinov (1902-1938), B. Hamrokulov (1902-1938), Kh.Shukurov (1900-1938) studied too, the enlightened and teacher A.Avloniy (1874-1931) taught the cadets Mother tongue and the Uzbek military specialists such as M.Mirbadalov, Sayyid Azamatbek Khudayarkhanov (1888-1938), R.Yokubov (1898-1957), T.Kyrgyzov (1899-1938) taught the cadets in different military subjects.

Many cadets, who graduated from the military commandership school, later worked at different military structures of 19 – Uzbek mountain-mounted divison. During the Stalin’s repression in 1937-1938s most of the Uzbek cadets studied at the Central Asian nations’ United military commandership school became innocent victims of the policy of repression unfairly blamed for espionage for the sake of any state and being “nationalists” or “counterrevolutionaries”.

Although the military schools trained (raised) military specialists for the sake of the soviet government, these schools did supportive function in providing the Red Army’s Uzbek national military units with local military cadres in the years of the soviet government too.

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